

EFFECTS OF BLENDED LEARNING STATION-ROTATION TEACHING STRATEGY ON COMPUTER SCIENCE EDUCATION STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENTS AT FEDERAL UNIVERSITY OTUOKE, BAYELSA STATE

BY

NGBARABARA, Prince Boniface, Ph.D

Department of Science Education, Federal University Otuoke Bayelsa State.

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0710-1205, ngbarabarapp@fuotuoke.edu.ng

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Abstract

This study examined the effects of the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy on the achievement of Computer Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The quasi-experimental pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted, involving a population of 133 Computer Science Education students, comprising 83 in the experimental group and 50 in the control group, drawn from the Department of Science Education. The experimental group was taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy, while the control group received instruction through the traditional lecture method. A 30-item instrument titled Internet of Things in Education Achievement Test (IoTEAT), developed by the researcher, was used for data collection. The instrument had a reliability index of .81 using the Kuder-Richardson₂₀ (KR-20) formula. Data were analysed using mean, standard deviation, and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at .05 level of significance. Findings revealed that students taught with the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy achieved significantly higher mean scores ($M = 36.71$, $SD = 6.94$) and greater mean gains (4.26) compared to those taught with the lecture method ($M = 32.91$, $SD = 7.03$; mean gain = 1.03). Results further showed that while female students (mean gain = 5.11) slightly outperformed their male counterparts (mean gain = 3.53) within the experimental group, the difference was not statistically significant. The ANCOVA results confirmed a significant effect of the teaching strategy ($F(1,130) = 312.89$, $p < 0.05$), but no significant gender effect ($F(1,80) = 2.51$, $p > 0.05$). The study concluded that the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy is more effective than the lecture method in improving student achievement and is equally beneficial across genders. It recommended wider adoption of the strategy in Computer Science Education and other STEM disciplines to promote inclusive and effective teaching and learning amongst others.

Keywords: Blended Learning, Station-Rotation, Teaching Strategy, Computer Science Education, Students' Achievements

Introduction

The fast-paced advancement of technology has significantly influenced various sectors, including education, where innovative teaching methods are transforming the way students learn. One such innovation is Blended Learning, which merges traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning to provide a more flexible and personalised learning environment. This educational approach has become popular due to its ability to cater to the diverse learning needs of students, allowing them to control aspects of their learning such as the pace and location

(Garrison and Kanuka, 2004; Graham, 2006; Hrastinski, 2019). As the demand for more dynamic and accessible education grows, especially in the field of Computer Science Education, educators are increasingly exploring blended learning strategies to improve student engagement and achievement.

Blended Learning refers to an educational approach that merges online digital media with traditional in-class methods, allowing students to have more control over the time, place, path, and pace of their learning (Horn and Staker, 2011). This pedagogical approach creates a more

dynamic and flexible learning environment, bridging the gap between conventional teaching techniques and the modern digital world. The blended learning model has proven effective in various educational settings, particularly in higher education, where students benefit from the combination of face-to-face interactions with online resources (Bonk and Graham, 2012). Blended learning, especially the Station-Rotation model, encourages active engagement, deeper learning, and better retention of course content, which is essential in subjects like Computer Science Education that require both theoretical understanding and practical application (Garrison and Vaughan, 2008).

The Station-Rotation model is one of the most widely implemented approaches within the broader concept of blended learning. It refers to an instructional method where students rotate through different learning stations on a fixed schedule, with at least one of the stations involving online learning. The model integrates face-to-face teacher-led instruction, collaborative group activities, and digital learning experiences to create a flexible and interactive learning environment (Horn and Staker, 2014). This approach differs from traditional classroom settings by offering students multiple modes of engagement, thus enabling teachers to differentiate instruction based on learners' abilities, interests, and progress. Horn and Staker (2015) described the Station-Rotation model as a sub-category of the rotation models of blended learning, alongside lab-rotation and individual-rotation models. In the Station-Rotation model, students move between teacher-led small groups, peer collaborative stations, and online learning activities. The structured rotation not only diversifies the learning process but also gives students opportunities to engage with content in different ways. Such variety helps sustain engagement and supports deeper understanding, especially in a subject like Computer Science

Education that combines theory and practice. One of the main benefits of the Station-Rotation model is its ability to personalise learning. Pane et al. (2015), in a large-scale study of personalised learning practices, found that station-rotation environments improve student engagement and learning outcomes by allowing for differentiated support. Teachers can use online platforms to track individual student progress and then target interventions during small-group or one-on-one sessions. This aligns with the principles of mastery learning, where students advance based on demonstrated understanding rather than uniform pacing (Bloom, 1984). In a study by Powell et al., (2015), the model was shown to promote peer-to-peer interaction through collaborative group activities, while the online stations fostered self-directed learning skills. This dual emphasis equips students with both academic knowledge and 21st-century competencies such as communication, collaboration, and problem-solving.

Teaching Strategies play a vital role in facilitating learning and ensuring students' mastery of the required content. A teaching strategy is essentially a method or approach used by educators to deliver knowledge and skills effectively (Joyce, Weil, and Calhoun, 2015). In this study, the teaching strategy under examination is the Blended Learning Station-Rotation model, which combines traditional and online instruction in a way that adapts to the unique challenges of teaching Computer Science. Effective teaching strategies, particularly in complex subjects like Computer Science Education, should not only convey information but also encourage students to apply their knowledge creatively and critically (Mishra and Koehler, 2006). The Station-Rotation model, as part of this blended learning approach, is designed to foster deeper understanding by allowing students to engage with content through

multiple perspectives, ultimately enhancing their academic performance.

In higher education and technical disciplines like Computer Science Education, the Station-Rotation model is particularly effective because it accommodates the dual demands of conceptual understanding and hands-on practice. For example, students can rotate from a teacher-led discussion on algorithmic theory to a collaborative station where they design flowcharts, and finally to an online coding platform where they test and refine their programs. This multimodal approach bridges the gap between theory and practice, ensuring students not only understand concepts but also apply them in problem-solving contexts (Yuan and Powell, 2013).

Computer Science Education focuses on teaching the principles and applications of computing, including programming, algorithms, and data structures (Goode, 2007). This field has grown in importance as digital technologies increasingly permeate every aspect of society. For students in Computer Science, mastering both theoretical concepts and practical applications is essential to succeed in an ever-evolving digital world. The combination of theory and practice in Computer Science Education requires teaching strategies that can bridge the gap between classroom learning and real-world application (Yadav et al., 2016). Therefore, incorporating a blended learning approach, specifically the Station-Rotation model, is crucial in enhancing the teaching and learning experience in this field. The diversity of learning stations allows students to alternate between theoretical discussions, coding exercises, and collaborative problem-solving, all of which are vital for their academic and professional development (Grover and Pea, 2013).

In this study, the focus is on how the Blended Learning Station-Rotation Teaching Strategy affects Students' Achievements in Computer

Science Education. Students' achievements refer to the measurable outcomes that demonstrate their understanding and mastery of course content (Bloom, 1956). Achievement is often assessed through exams, assignments, and practical projects, especially in fields like Computer Science, where both theoretical knowledge and practical skills are equally important (Shute et al., 2016). Academic success is not solely based on how well students perform on tests but also on their ability to apply what they have learned to solve complex problems (Marsh et al., 2006). In the context of Computer Science Education, student achievement can be seen in their proficiency with programming languages, their understanding of algorithms, and their capacity to design and implement effective solutions to computational problems (Hattie, 2009). The Station-Rotation model, by providing varied learning environments, supports students in developing these critical skills, thereby contributing to their overall academic success irrespective of gender.

Gender is a crucial variable in educational research because it shapes how learners experience teaching and learning innovations such as the blended learning station-rotation model. Studies show mixed outcomes: while some report no significant gender differences in achievement within blended learning (Delgado and Wardlow, 2019), others suggest that females often excel due to stronger self-regulation and time management (Rovai and Baker, 2005; Xu and Jaggars, 2014), whereas males may display higher confidence with technology use (Li and Kirkup, 2007). In contexts like Nigeria, where socio-cultural and economic factors influence access to education (Okeke, Nzewi, and Njoku, 2012), examining gender ensures equity and inclusivity. Thus, incorporating gender as a variable allows the researcher to determine whether innovative strategies such as station-rotation benefit male and female students

equally, making findings more relevant for policy and practice.

Given the increasing importance of technology in education, it is essential to explore teaching strategies that can improve learning outcomes in technical fields like Computer Science Education. The Blended Learning Station-Rotation Teaching Strategy offers a promising approach by combining traditional and online instruction in a way that meets the diverse needs of learners. This study aims to investigate how this teaching strategy impacts the achievement of Computer Science Education students at Federal University Otuoke. With the field of Computer Science Education demanding both theoretical understanding and hands-on practice, the Station-Rotation model presents a comprehensive approach to learning, ensuring that students not only absorb knowledge but also apply it effectively. Understanding the impact of this model on students' achievements will provide valuable insights for educators looking to enhance teaching and learning practices in higher education, particularly in technical disciplines like Computer Science.

By investigating the effects of the Blended Learning Station-Rotation Teaching Strategy on students' achievements, this study seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on educational innovation in the digital age. As the demands of the global workforce shift towards more technologically proficient individuals, universities must adopt teaching strategies that can equip students with the necessary skills to thrive. This research will provide insights into the effectiveness of the Station-Rotation model in improving student performance, thereby offering a pathway for more effective teaching strategies in Computer Science Education. The findings from this study could help shape future pedagogical practices, ensuring that students are better prepared to meet the challenges of a rapidly evolving digital world.

Statement of Problem

The rapid technological advancements and the increasing demand for digital literacy have placed immense pressure on higher education institutions to adopt innovative teaching strategies that can meet the evolving needs of students, particularly in fields like Computer Science Education. Traditional teaching methods, which often rely on lecture-based delivery, are increasingly being questioned for their effectiveness in fostering deep learning and practical skill acquisition. In Computer Science Education, students are expected not only to grasp complex theoretical concepts but also to develop practical problem-solving skills that can be applied in real-world scenarios. However, many students struggle to achieve high levels of proficiency due to the disconnect between classroom learning and practical application, resulting in low achievement scores and retention rates.

The Blended Learning Station-Rotation Teaching Strategy, which combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning and practical station activities, has emerged as a promising approach to address these challenges. This model allows students to rotate between various learning stations, where they can engage in different modes of learning such as group discussions, individual study, and hands-on practice. By integrating both online and offline components, this strategy offers a more personalised and flexible learning experience that caters to diverse learning styles. Despite its potential, the effect of the Blended Learning Station-Rotation model on students' achievements in Computer Science Education, particularly in Nigerian universities, remains under-researched.

At Federal University Otuoke in Bayelsa State, where Computer Science Education students are expected to master both theoretical and practical aspects of the curriculum, the traditional lecture-based approach has often led to suboptimal

learning outcomes. There is a pressing need to explore alternative teaching strategies that could enhance students' academic achievements and better prepare them for the demands of the digital world. However, limited empirical evidence exists on the specific impact of the Station-Rotation model within the context of the Nigerian tertiary institution, especially in relation to Computer Science Education. This gap in the literature calls for a focused examination into how this innovative teaching strategy influences students' academic achievement in terms of knowledge acquisition, practical application, and overall performance. Thus, the study sought to close this gap by examining the effect of the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy on Computer Science Education students' achievement at Federal University Otuoke. By investigating the effect of this teaching strategy, the study aimed to provide insight into how blended learning models can be effectively implemented to improve educational outcomes in technical disciplines like Computer Science Education. Mastering the influence of this model on student achievement will not only contribute to the body of knowledge on blended learning but also offer practical recommendations for lecturers seeking to enhance teaching and learning in Computer Science Education.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy on Computer Science Education students' achievements at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. Specifically, the purpose of the study was to determine the:

1. Mean achievement scores of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group) and those

taught using lecture method (Control Group).

2. Mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group).

Research Questions

The following two research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy and those taught using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy in both pre-test and post-test?

Hypotheses

The following two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using lecture method (Control Group).
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group).

Research Methods

The quasi-experimental design involving a pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group was adopted for the study. The total population comprised 133 students of the Department of Science Education (Computer Science Education option). Since the population size was manageable, no sampling was employed. The participants were assigned to two groups: an experimental group of 83 students, who were taught using the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy, and a control group of 50 students, who were taught using the conventional lecture method. Both groups were administered a pretest before treatment to determine their entry-level knowledge, and a posttest after treatment to measure the effect of the intervention on their achievement.

The instrument for data collection was a 30-item Internet of Things in Education Achievement Test (IoTEAT) developed by the researcher. The reliability of the instrument was estimated using

the Kuder-Richardson₂₀ (KR-20) formula, which yielded a reliability coefficient of .81, indicating acceptable internal consistency. The data relating to the research questions were analysed using mean and standard deviation, while Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was employed to test the null hypotheses by controlling for pretest differences between the groups. The decision rule for hypothesis testing was to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) if the significance value of the F-ratio was less than .05; otherwise, the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy and those taught using lecture method in both pre-test and post-test?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviations of Students Taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy and those Taught using Lecture Method in both Pre-Test and Post-test

Group	N	Pretest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest Mean	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
Experimental	83	32.45	5.82	36.71	6.94	4.26
Control	50	31.88	6.11	32.91	7.03	1.03

Table 1 presents the mean achievement scores, standard deviations, and mean gains of students in the experimental and control groups for both pretest and posttest. The pretest mean scores of the experimental group ($M = 32.45, SD = 5.82$) and control group ($M = 31.88, SD = 6.11$) were very close, indicating that the two groups were comparable in their initial achievement levels in Internet of Things (IoT) in Education. However, in the posttest, the experimental group ($M = 36.71, SD = 6.94$) outperformed the control group ($M = 32.91, SD = 7.03$). The calculated mean gain further shows that the experimental

group improved by 4.26 points, compared to 1.03 points for the control group. This result indicated that the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy enhanced students' achievement more effectively than the conventional lecture method.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores and standard deviation of male and female students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy in both pre-test and post-test?

Table 2: Mean Achievement Scores and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation Teaching Strategy in both Pre-test and Post-test

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest Mean	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
Male	45	32.89	5.77	36.42	7.12	3.53
Female	38	31.97	5.89	37.08	6.74	5.11

Table 2 shows the mean achievement scores, standard deviations, and mean gains of male and female students in the experimental group who were taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy. At pretest, the mean scores of males ($M = 32.89$, $SD = 5.77$) and females ($M = 31.97$, $SD = 5.89$) were very close, suggesting that both groups had similar entry-level knowledge. After the treatment, the posttest mean scores indicated improvement for both males ($M = 36.42$, $SD = 7.12$) and females ($M =$

37.08 , $SD = 6.74$). The mean gain values further revealed that females improved by 5.11 points, slightly higher than the 3.53 points recorded for males. This suggests that while the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy enhanced achievement for both genders, female students appeared to benefit marginally more.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group) and those taught using lecture method (Control Group)

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	Sig. (p)	Decision
Corrected Model	14672.38	2	7336.19	162.41	0.000	*
Covariate (Pretest)	528.64	1	528.64	11.70	0.001	
Group (Treatment)	14143.74	1	14143.74	312.89	0.000	Reject H ₀₁
Error	5853.92	130	45.03			
Total	578040.00	133				
Corrected Total	20526.30	132				

***Significant at $p < 0.05$**

Table 3 presents the summary of ANCOVA comparing the mean achievement scores of students in the experimental and control groups after adjusting for pretest scores. The result showed that the treatment's effect was statistically significant, $F(1,130) = 312.89$, $p < 0.05$. Since the calculated probability value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) was rejected. This

implies that there was a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy and those taught using the lecture method, in favour of the experimental group.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female

students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-

Rotation teaching strategy (Experimental Group).

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA analysis of significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching (Experimental Group)

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	Sig. (p)	Decision
Corrected Model	291.86	2	145.93	3.18	0.045	
Covariate (Pretest)	176.24	1	176.24	3.83	0.053	
Gender	115.62	1	115.62	2.51	0.116	Do not reject H ₀₂
Error	3714.89	80	46.44			
Total	423792.00	83				
Corrected Total	4006.75	82				

*Not significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 4 presents the summary of ANCOVA comparing the mean achievement scores of male and female students in the experimental group after adjusting for pretest scores. The result showed that the effect of gender on students' achievement was not statistically significant, $F(1,80) = 2.51, p > 0.05$. Since the calculated probability value of 0.116 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Internet of Things (IoT) in Education using the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy, suggesting that the strategy was equally effective across genders.

Discussion of Findings

The results of this study revealed that the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy significantly improved students' achievement in Internet of Things (IoT) in Education compared to the traditional lecture method. Table 1 shows that although the pretest mean scores of the experimental groups were nearly identical, the posttest mean scores diverged considerably, with the experimental group achieving a mean of 36.71 while the

control group attained only 32.91. The mean gain analysis further highlighted this difference, with the experimental group recording a 4.26-point improvement against the 1.03 points gained by the control group. This pattern of results confirms the hypothesis that interactive, learner-centred methods such as blended learning can enhance achievement more effectively than conventional approaches.

These findings align with earlier studies that have demonstrated the effectiveness of blended learning models in higher education. For instance, Bernard et al. (2014) reported that blended learning produces higher student achievement than purely face-to-face or purely online learning, owing to its balance of flexibility and interactivity. Similarly, Owston et al., (2013) observed that students exposed to blended formats displayed greater motivation and performed better academically compared to peers taught exclusively through lectures. Within the Nigerian context, Adeoye and Adanikin (2019) found that integrating digital platforms into instructional delivery significantly improved undergraduate students' engagement and learning outcomes. The results of this present study, therefore, corroborate these earlier conclusions by showing that the station-rotation model, which structures learning across teacher-

led, online, and collaborative stations, provided students with richer opportunities to consolidate their understanding of IoT concepts.

The ANCOVA results presented in Table 3 confirmed that the observed differences in achievement between the experimental and control groups were statistically significant, $F(1,130) = 312.89, p < 0.05$. This suggests that the effect was not due to pre-existing differences but rather to the treatment itself. This finding is consistent with the work of Horn and Staker (2015), who argued that the structured rotation of students across learning stations promotes personalised learning, thereby enabling deeper understanding and retention of complex concepts. In Computer Science Education specifically, Zydney and Warner (2016) also demonstrated that students learning through blended station-rotation methods developed stronger problem-solving and coding skills compared to those taught in lecture-only environments. The current study, therefore, adds further empirical weight to the argument that blended learning strategies are not only pedagogically sound but also contextually adaptable to Nigerian universities.

In relation to gender, the results presented in Table 2 showed that both male ($M = 36.42, SD = 7.12$) and female ($M = 37.08, SD = 6.74$) students in the experimental group experienced significant achievement gains after the intervention. While female students recorded a slightly higher mean gain (5.11) compared to their male counterparts (3.53), the difference was marginal. The ANCOVA results in Table 4 indicated that this gender difference was not statistically significant, $F(1,80) = 2.51, p > 0.05$. Thus, the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy proved equally effective for both male and female learners.

This outcome aligns with the findings of Adesope and Rud (2019), who reported that blended instructional strategies tend to minimise traditional gender disparities in achievement by

providing diverse modes of engagement that cater to different learning preferences. Similarly, Martin and Bolliger (2018) argued that digital-enhanced pedagogies create inclusive learning environments where both genders can thrive equally. A study by Yusuf and Afolabi (2010) in Nigeria also found no significant gender differences in computer-assisted learning outcomes, further supporting the results of this present study. These findings collectively suggest that when learning environments are diversified and inclusive, gender ceases to be a major determinant of achievement outcomes.

The implication of these results is twofold. First, the significant improvement in the achievement of students taught using the station-rotation strategy indicated that such methods could serve as a practical alternative to lecture-based teaching in Nigerian universities, particularly in fields like Computer Science Education that require both conceptual understanding and practical application. Secondly, the lack of significant gender differences underscores the potential of blended learning to foster equity in access to quality educational outcomes, a priority for both national and international educational policy frameworks.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy significantly enhanced the achievement of Computer Science Education students in Internet of Things (IoT) in Education at Federal University Otuoke, Bayelsa State. The experimental group recorded higher mean scores and greater mean gains than their counterparts taught with the conventional lecture method, demonstrating the pedagogical effectiveness of the Station-Rotation model in encouraging deeper understanding and active participation. Furthermore, although females in the experimental group recorded slightly higher mean gains than their male counterparts, the

ANCOVA analysis revealed no significant gender differences, implying that the strategy is equitable and beneficial to all learners regardless of gender. These findings imply that the integration of innovative instructional strategies such as Blended Learning Station-Rotation can bridge gaps associated with traditional teaching methods, thereby equipping students with practical and theoretical competencies needed in technology-driven fields like Computer Science Education. The non-significant gender differences further suggest that the adoption of this strategy can promote inclusivity and gender equity in higher education. This study further underscores the need for lecturers and policymakers to embrace blended learning approaches, particularly the Station-Rotation model, as a viable means of improving students' learning outcomes in technology-related disciplines. By encouraging active engagement, collaboration, and personalised learning, this strategy not only enhances academic achievement but also prepares students for the dynamic demands of the 21st-century knowledge economy.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on findings;

1. Lecturers in Computer Science Education should adopt the Blended Learning Station-Rotation teaching strategy as a core instructional method.
2. University Management and education policymakers should provide regular workshops and professional development programmes to train lecturers on the effective design, integration, and facilitation of Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategies.
3. Since the findings showed no significant gender difference in achievement, the Blended Learning Station-Rotation strategy

should be promoted as an equitable instructional model.

4. The adoption of Blended Learning Station-Rotation should not be limited to Computer Science Education. Other departments, especially within the STEM disciplines, should be encouraged to apply the strategy to enhance student achievement across the university.

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